

A Cross-Sectional Comparative Study on Peace Levels of Rajyoga Meditation Practitioners and Non-Practitioners

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Abstract

Peace is a vital force for mental and social well-being in these modern times. Today, people all over the world are searching for true peace. Peace is, actually inner harmony, serenity and a deep state of mind rather than the situation of no external conflict. Rajyoga meditation, practiced at *Prajapita Brahma Kumaris Ishwariya Vishwa Vidyalaya*, recognizes the self as a conscious soul, recognizes the Supreme soul as supreme Father and connects with Him through mental communion. This meditation practice empowers the soul and brings peace into everyday life. This research paper compares the levels of peace of Rajyoga meditation practitioners and non-practitioners. The Peace Scale 2025 (Yellow Pond, India) is Indian scale which measures six dimensions: inner calm, kindness, connection, hope, safety and acceptance. The study's research design was comparative and data analysis was conducted using descriptive statistics and independent t-tests. A total of 50 adult participants were selected through the purposive sampling technique (25 Rajyoga meditation practitioners from Brahma Kumaris Rajyoga Centre, Chanakya Place, New Delhi and 25 non-practitioners from the general population). The results revealed a large difference between the two groups, with Rajyoga meditation practitioners showing higher mean scores on all peace dimensions than non-practitioners. The results found that Rajyoga meditation is an effective tool for enhancing overall peace and emotional well-being. Research shows that peace can be found through spiritual practice and meditation, rather than seeking it externally through material sources. Rajyoga meditation is a holistic approach to improve balance, resilience and positive mental health. The results inspire educational, workplace and community programs to integrate Rajyoga-based practices to promote peaceful, value-driven lives and collective well-being.

Keywords: Rajyoga Meditation, Peace, Inner Calm, Hope, Acceptance, Psychological Well-being

1. Introduction

In this era of technology, increasing stress, depression, conflict and uncertainty, finding inner and outer peace has become critical for psychological well-being. Peace is not simply the absence of conflict, but also experiencing harmony, hope, compassion and self-acceptance. The Peace Scale 2025 [8] views peace as a multidimensional unit, encompassing inner calm, kindness, connection, hope, safety and acceptance (Murugesan, Shivam, & Suresh, 2025) [8].

Rajyoga meditation, imparted by the Brahma Kumaris World Spiritual University (BKWSU), emphasizes connecting with the Supreme Source through self-consciousness, positive thinking and self-transformation (Pandiamani, 2019) [14]. Its aim is to achieve inner peace and self-mastery without any rituals or mantras. Studies have shown that Rajyoga meditation improves psychological

well-being, emotional regulation and resilience (Gupta & Mohan, 2020; Kumar & Shivam, 2023) [3, 7].

As, limited research has studied the relative levels of peace between practitioners of Rajyoga and those who do not, using a standard Indian tool as the Peace Scale 2025 [8]. Hence, this study aims to fill this gap.

2. Literature Review

2.1 The Concept of Peace

'Peace' is a transformative state of inner peace, good relationships, security and self-acceptance (Jha, 2020) [4]. The UNESCO Declaration of Peace (2016) [5] identifies peace as a state of mind characterized by education, empathy and moral consciousness. The Peace Scale 2025 [8] addresses this through six measurable domains that together reveal complete peace.

2.2 Rajyoga Meditation and Peace of Mind

Rajyoga meditation, which is embedded in the *Brahma Kumaris'* spiritual philosophy, focuses on "think right, see right, speak right, hear right and do right." Research shows that people who practice Rajyoga exhibit less anxiety and greater emotional balance than those who do not (Singh and Kumar, 2022) [12]. Neuropsychological studies also link meditation to increased alpha brainwave activity, which is associated with relaxation and peace of mind (Davidson and Kabat-Zinn, 2003) [2].

2.3 Previous Comparative Studies

Several comparative studies show that Rajyoga meditation has a positive impact on mental health indicators such as calmness, emotional stability and resilience. Regular practitioners report less symptoms of stress, anxiety and depression than those who do not. Shivakumar and Nirmala (2018) [13] found that those who practiced yoga and meditation experienced greater life satisfaction and less anger. Rathi and Sharma (2020) [10] reported significant differences in emotional stability and social connectedness among those who meditated regularly. Kumar and Pandiamani (2024) [6] emphasized that Rajyoga practice increases acceptance, reduces internal conflicts and improves interpersonal relationships. Ramesh *et al.* (2013) [11] conducted a cross-sectional comparative study and found that those who practiced Rajyoga meditation had significantly higher levels of positive thinking and positive emotions than those who did not. Patel *et al.* (2020) [9] found that compared to mindfulness meditation and non-meditation, Rajyoga was particularly effective in increasing self-control and emotional resilience and reducing stress. Chalageri *et al.* (2021) [1] found that even one month of Rajyoga practice significantly reduced depression, anxiety, stress and pain, as well as improved functional independence in participants with spinal cord injuries.

2.4 Research Gap

Despite the fact several studies explored psychological benefits of meditation, few have empirically compared peace levels using an indigenous, multidimensional tool such as the Peace Scale 2025 [8]. This study, thus, examines whether Rajyoga Meditation practitioners experience higher peace than non-practitioners.

3. Objectives of the study

- To evaluate the level of peace among Rajyoga Meditation practitioners and non-practitioners.
- To explore the overall peace score difference among practitioners and non-practitioners.

4. Hypotheses

H₀: There is no significant difference in overall peace scores between Rajyoga Meditation practitioners and non-practitioners.

H₁: Rajyoga Meditation practitioners will have significantly higher peace scores than non-practitioners.

5. Methodology

5.1 Research Design

This study adopted a *cross-sectional comparative* research

design. This design was selected to examine and compare the peace levels of two distinct groups—Rajyoga Meditation Practitioners and Non-Practitioners—at a single point in time.

5.2 Sample

A total number of 50 adult participants aged 18-65 years were selected using purposive sampling technique. Group-A 25 Rajyoga Meditation practitioners (above 3 year of regular meditation practice at Brahma Kumaris centers and home). Rajyoga meditation practitioners were selected from Brahma Kumaris Rajyoga Centre, Chanakya Place, New Delhi. Group-B 25 Non-practitioners (from the general population no formal meditation or yoga practice).

5.3 Data Collection Tool

Peace Scale 2025 [8] (Yellow Pond India, 2025) [8] developed by Dr. Suresh Kumar Murugesan, Dr. Pandiamani Sivam (BK) and Dr. V. Suresh. It comprises of 30 items covering six dimensions which are Inner Calm, Kindness, Connection, Hope, Safety and Acceptance. Items rated on a 5-point scale (Always = 5 to Never = 1). Reliability of the scale is $\alpha = 0.91$. Validity of the scale is expert-validated and culturally standardized.

5.4 Procedure

The questionnaire was administered to both groups after obtaining consent. Responses were scored according to the instructions. Mean differences were compared of both groups.

5.5 Analysis

Descriptive statistics (Mean, SD) and inferential statistics (t-test) were used to compare the peace levels between the two groups.

6. Results

6.1 Results of both groups are given in details.

Table 1: Demographic Summary comparing Rajyoga Meditation Practitioners and Non-Practitioners

Age		
Group	Mean Age	SD
Rajyoga Practitioners (A)	39.14 years	12.54
Non-Practitioners (B)	34.96 years	11.50
Gender Distribution		
Gender	Practitioners (A)	Non-Practitioners (B)
Male	12	12
Female	13	13
Educational Qualification		
Post-Graduate (PG)	07	02
Graduate	11	21
Secondary	07	02
Occupation		
Job	11	16
Retired	04	05
Housewife	06	02
Own Business	03	-
Student	01	02
Marital Status		
Married	16	16
Single	09	09

Rajyoga Meditation Practitioners rise to be slightly elder on average (≈ 39 vs 35 years). Gender distribution is balanced in both groups. A higher educational level (PG) is seen among Practitioners group. Majority in both groups are employed but Practitioners include more housewife participants. Married participants form the largest portion in both groups.

Table 2: Mean Score of Peace Dimensions

Dimensions	Practitioners Mean (A)	Non-Practitioners Mean (B)
Inner Calm	4.25	2.98
Kindness	4.38	3.18
Connection	4.30	3.10
Hope	4.46	2.99
Safety	4.51	2.90
Acceptance	4.53	3.30

The mean scores for Rajyoga meditation practitioners move closer to the “Always” end of the scale in all dimensions while non-practitioners remain gathered around “Sometimes” and “Rarely”. The gaps are inclusive in Hope, Safety and Acceptance, reinforcing the probable impact of Rajyoga meditation practice on emotional and psychological health. Kindness and Connection also show noticeable improvements for meditation practitioners.

The t-test analysis reveals highly significant differences between Rajyoga meditation practitioners and non-practitioners across all well-being dimensions, with p-values below 0.001 in every case.

Table 3: T-Test Results (Five-Point Scale)

Peace Dimensions	t-value	p-value	Practitioner Mean (A)	Non-Practitioner Mean (B)
Inner Calm	11.44	0.0000	4.25	2.98
Kindness	10.14	0.0000	4.38	3.18
Connection	10.55	0.0000	4.30	3.10
Hope	13.09	0.0000	4.46	2.99
Safety	14.52	0.0000	4.51	2.90
Acceptance	11.04	0.0000	4.53	3.30

All dimensions show large t-values and extremely low p-values, confirming statistically significant differences favoring Rajyoga meditation practitioners. The difference is strongest in Safety ($t=14.52$), Hope ($t=13.09$) and Inner Calm ($t=11.44$). Practitioners average near “Always” responses, while non-practitioners leaning toward “Sometimes” or lower.

These results support that Rajyoga meditation practice is significantly associated with higher subjective well-being and positive psychological outcomes. The findings from this analysis strongly suggest that regular Rajyoga meditation is associated with higher levels of psychological well-being, as demonstrated by significantly higher scores in all measured domains among Rajyoga meditation practitioners compared to non-practitioners. Rajyoga meditation practitioners scored significantly higher on all six dimensions and overall peace. The results reject the null hypothesis and confirm that Rajyoga meditation has a positive effect on peace.

7. Discussion

These results are consistent with previous studies that show that meditation increases peace, compassion and

psychological safety (Kabat-Zinn, 2016) [5]. Raja Yoga meditation promotes self-awareness and divine connection, leading to increased stability and acceptance (Pandiamani, 2019) [14]. The significantly higher peace scores among practitioners indicate that consistent meditation improves overall well-being-emotional, social and spiritual. This supports the idea that peace can be cultivated through mental discipline and a value-based life. The Peace Scale 2025 [8] effectively captured multidimensional growth, proving useful in measuring subjective inner harmony in the Indian population.

8. Conclusion

The study concluded that of Rajyoga meditation practitioners experienced significantly greater levels of peace across all dimensions compared to non-practitioners. Rajyoga meditation enhances feelings of inner peace, compassion, connection, hope, security and acceptance. Hence, it can be recommended as a simple practice to promote overall peace and well-being in educational, corporate and community settings.

9. Limitations: This study has some limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the sample size was limited to 50 participants, which may make it difficult to generalize the results to a larger population. Second, the study trusted on self-report measures which are subject to personal interpretation and may introduce subjective bias into participants' responses. Future studies with larger, longitudinal samples and objective measures are recommended to increase the validity and depth of the outcomes.

10. Suggestions for Future Research

Future research could expand the scope of this study in several areas. Longitudinal intervention studies could be conducted to measure changes in peace levels over time, providing insight into the long-term effects of Rajyoga meditation practice. Moreover, cross-cultural validation of the Peace Scale 2025 [8] would enhance its efficacy and reliability across different cultural and demographic groups. Furthermore, future research could focus on exploring the relationship between peace, emotional intelligence and mindfulness, providing a deeper understanding of how these interconnected psychological features contribute to human well-being and inner harmony.

11. Ethical Consideration

Participation was voluntary with informed consent obtained. Anonymity and confidentiality were ensured.

12. Acknowledgement

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